

1 Unsupervised Learning-Based 2 Operational Regime Discovery and 3 Weather Sensitivity Analysis of a 4 Residential Photovoltaic Battery 5 System for Energy Management

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7

8 Abstract

9 Behind-the-meter photovoltaic battery systems exhibit heterogeneous daily operating behaviors
10 shaped by weather conditions, household demand, storage control, and grid interaction. Identifying
11 these operational regimes is essential for improving forecasting, system control, and policy design,
12 particularly where labeled operational data are unavailable. This study proposes a fully label-free,
13 unsupervised framework to identify recurring daily operational regimes in a residential
14 photovoltaic battery system and to quantify regime-specific weather sensitivities. Fourteen months
15 of high-resolution operational data from a residential photovoltaic battery system in Yangon,
16 Myanmar, are analyzed. Daily features capturing photovoltaic generation, electricity consumption,
17 grid exchange, battery charging and discharging, state of charge, and self-consumption are derived
18 from intraday profiles. Isolation Forest outlier detection removes anomalous operating days,
19 yielding 411 representative days for analysis. K-means clustering identifies four distinct
20 operational regimes, validated using Gaussian Mixture Models, hierarchical clustering, and
21 density-based methods. Principal component analysis confirms clear separation and
22 interpretability of the identified regimes. Cluster-wise standardized regression models link daily
23 photovoltaic energy production to meteorological drivers. Solar irradiance is the dominant
24 explanatory variable across all regimes, with effect sizes increasing from grid-dependent to self-
25 sufficient operating modes. Temperature and relative humidity exhibit regime-dependent
26 secondary effects, while wind speed plays a limited role. Seasonal analysis reveals systematic
27 shifts in regime prevalence driven by climatic conditions. The proposed framework provides an
28 interpretable and transferable approach for diagnosing real-world photovoltaic battery system

29 behavior and yields actionable regime labels that support regime-aware forecasting and adaptive
30 energy management in distributed energy systems.

31 **Keywords:** Photovoltaic systems, Unsupervised learning, Clustering algorithms, Load profiling,
32 Feature engineering, Renewable energy integration.

33 1. Introduction

34 Residential photovoltaic-battery systems are transforming distribution-level power flows, yet
35 their daily operating modes are rarely labeled or well understood. Rapid deployment of residential
36 photovoltaic systems combined with energy storage contributes to sustainability and
37 decarbonization goals, but also introduces additional complexity for power system planning,
38 operational stability, and economic assessment [1,2]. In practice, similar photovoltaic generation
39 levels can correspond to fundamentally different operating conditions depending on battery
40 charging, discharging, and grid exchange, making daily system behavior difficult to interpret and
41 manage. Daily behavior emerges from weather-driven generation, user demand, and opaque
42 control logic, and typically lacks labels, motivating unsupervised learning [3]. Recent zero-label
43 domain adaptation can forecast PV power at new sites without labeled targets [4].

44 Prior work excels at supervised PV forecasting using statistical and machine learning methods
45 that ingest irradiance, temperature, or sky images [5,6], delivering accurate short-term predictions,
46 but typically relying on labeled historical outputs, which can constrain transferability across
47 systems or operating contexts. Post-adoption analytics predominantly focus on consumption-only
48 load profiling from smart-meter data, identifying appliance signatures and usage patterns [7,8].
49 Unsupervised clustering methods, particularly K-means, have proven effective for customer
50 segmentation and daily load-shape analysis [9,10], yet rarely integrate production, grid exchange,
51 and battery metrics into a unified household view. Deep clustering approaches such as deep
52 adaptive fuzzy clustering (DAFC) achieve state-of-the-art performance on large datasets [11], but
53 joint modeling of prosumer behavior remains underexplored.

54 Weather effects on PV yield and demand are well-established: temperature drives cooling
55 loads, while irradiance and cloud cover determine generation [12,13]. Recent work shows that
56 grouping days by weather patterns before training deep learning models improves day-ahead PV
57 forecasting [14], and comfort-aware cloud energy storage schemes mitigate seasonal variability
58 [15]. However, studies connecting weather to unsupervised household-level operational regimes
59 remain limited, especially in tropical and monsoon climates. PV-battery scheduling research
60 employs model predictive control, rule-based schemes, and reinforcement learning [16,17], yet
61 daily operation often deviates due to user actions, comfort preferences, and device constraints.
62 Unsupervised discovery of operational archetypes can reveal how systems behave over long
63 horizons and provide regime labels for policy conditioning. Unlike traditional load profiling
64 studies that focus solely on electricity consumption, this work captures the coupled dynamics of
65 on-site generation, battery storage, and grid interaction at the household level.

66 The survey of prior art presented above reveals that three critical gaps persist: (1) prior
 67 clustering typically uses short durations or single-channel demand data rather than long-horizon,
 68 multi-feature prosumer representations; (2) few studies connect unsupervised operational
 69 archetypes with daily weather drivers and quantify regime-specific outcomes through multivariate
 70 regression; (3) many papers report single clustering results without cross-method validation or
 71 agreement measures. To address these gaps, this study applies a robust unsupervised learning
 72 framework to a comprehensive, long-term dataset from a residential PV-battery system in Yangon,
 73 Myanmar. A simplified architecture of the system under study is shown in Figure 1.

74
 75 **Figure. 1.** Simplified architecture of a grid-connected hybrid PV-battery system under study.

76 A label-free framework is proposed that discovers operational archetypes from 14 months of
 77 residential PV-BESS data (5-10 min resolution), validates them across clustering methods, and
 78 links their occurrence to meteorological drivers through multivariate regression. Unlike supervised
 79 forecasting or EMS/control studies, the approach explains how and when households shift among
 80 self-sufficient, weather-limited, and grid-dependent regimes, with implications for adaptive
 81 control and dynamic tariffs. The framework employs Isolation Forest outlier detection, objective
 82 K selection via elbow and silhouette analysis, and method comparison (K-means, GMM,
 83 hierarchical, DBSCAN) to ensure robustness. The dataset spans 14 months at 5-10-minute
 84 resolution (104,036 raw records; 56,623 daytime points after cleaning), integrating synchronized
 85 channels for production, consumption, grid exchange, battery power, and state of charge. Daily
 86 features encapsulating holistic system behavior (self-consumption ratio, grid dependency ratio, net
 87 battery usage) are engineered and used to identify recurring operational archetypes. After
 88 excluding 5 outlier days (1.2%) via Isolation Forest, 411 normal operation days are clustered into

89 four distinct regimes using K-means with K-means++ initialization. Cluster-wise multivariate
90 standardized ordinary least squares regression quantifies weather sensitivities, revealing irradiance
91 as the dominant predictor ($\beta^*=0.22-0.79$) with regime-dependent temperature and humidity
92 effects. The work presented in this paper achieves three primary contributions:

- 93 • Reproducible pipeline: A validated framework integrating outlier detection, daily feature
94 engineering, clustering with objective K selection, and robustness validation using PCA,
95 normalized mutual information, and method comparison across K-means, GMM,
96 hierarchical, and DBSCAN.
- 97 • Archetypes with weather linkage: Four interpretable regimes identified and quantified
98 through cluster-wise multivariate regression, revealing regime-specific sensitivities to
99 irradiance, temperature, humidity, and wind.
- 100 • Regime-specific performance: Intraday profiles and standardized weather coefficients
101 quantified per regime, demonstrating how operational constraints and behavioral patterns
102 decouple consumption from available solar resource.

103 Therefore, it is demonstrated in this paper that unsupervised learning with explicit weather linkage
104 provides a practical, label-free basis for diagnosing real-world PV-battery behavior and for
105 designing weather-aware control, adaptive tariff mechanisms, and sizing methods that improve
106 integration of distributed resources.

107 The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The proposed method and data are described in
108 Section 2, while the results are discussed in Section 3. Section 4 outlines the engineering
109 implications of the identified operational regimes. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

110 2. Method

111 The analytical pipeline of the proposed methodology is illustrated in Figure. 2. Raw high-
112 resolution data are preprocessed and used to engineer a set of daily features capturing system
113 behavior. Outlier detection removes anomalous days before clustering. The feature set is
114 standardized before applying multiple clustering algorithms (K-means, GMM, hierarchical,
115 DBSCAN) with comparative validation. The optimal K-means solution is linked to weather
116 through multivariate regression. The proposed pipeline is not tied to a specific climate region, as
117 it relies on generic daily operational features rather than location-specific assumptions. All
118 required inputs correspond to standard measurements recorded by commonly deployed residential
119 photovoltaic battery system loggers, supporting portability across sites and geographic contexts.

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121
122 Figure. 2. The proposed method pipeline from raw PV-BESS data to operational archetypes via feature engineering,
123 outlier detection, clustering comparison, and weather linkage.

124 2.1 Site and Data Preprocessing

125 Fourteen months of sub-hourly data were collected from a residential PV-battery system in
126 Yangon, Myanmar (UTC+06:30), logged at 5-10 min resolution. The raw archive includes 104,036
127 timestamps across day and night. For analysis, only periods with nonzero PV output were retained,
128 key-channel gaps were dropped, and all times were aligned to local time, yielding 56,623 daytime
129 records. Power series were integrated over each time step using the trapezoidal rule to form daily

130 energies (kWh). Unless noted, grid power greater than 0 indicates import and battery power greater
 131 than 0 indicates discharge.

132 2.2 Daily Feature Engineering

133 Logger signals include Production Power (W), Consumption Power (W), Grid Power (W),
 134 Purchasing Power (W), Feed-in Power (W), Battery Power (W), Charging Power (W), Discharging
 135 Power (W), and State of Charge (SoC, %). From these high-resolution time series, a suite of daily
 136 features was engineered to capture holistic system behavior. The key derived features are the Self-
 137 Consumption Ratio (SCR) and the Grid Dependency Ratio (GDR), which comprise key metrics
 138 for evaluating system performance [18,19]. These Ratios are defined as follows:

$$139 \quad SCR = \frac{\text{Daily PV Energy} - \text{Daily Grid Export}}{\text{Daily PV Energy}} = \frac{E_{pv} - E_{\text{export}}}{E_{pv}} \quad (1)$$

$$141 \quad GDR = \frac{\text{Daily Grid Import}}{\text{Daily Consumption}} = \frac{E_{\text{import}}}{E_{\text{load}}} \quad (2)$$

142
 143 where E_{pv} , E_{export} , E_{load} and E_{import} represent the daily integrated energy from PV production, grid
 144 export, consumption, and grid import, respectively. The Battery Net Usage ($E_{\text{batt, net}}$) quantifies
 145 the net energy contribution from the battery storage on a daily basis:

$$146 \quad E_{\text{batt, net}} = E_{\text{batt, disch}} - E_{\text{batt, ch}} \quad (3)$$

147 where $E_{\text{batt, disch}}$ and $E_{\text{batt, ch}}$ are the total daily energy discharged from and charged to the battery,
 148 respectively. In addition, the Self-Sufficiency Ratio (SSR) is used to quantify the fraction of
 149 household electricity demand supplied by on-site resources and is computed as:

$$150 \quad SSR = 1 - GDR = 1 - \frac{E_{\text{import}}}{E_{\text{load}}} \quad (4)$$

151 Table 1 summarizes the engineered daily features used for clustering.

152 Table 1. Description of Engineered Features.

Feature Name	Type	Unit	Description/ Computation
Daily PV Energy	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Total daily energy generated by the PV system. Computed by time-weighted integration of PV power over daytime:
Daily Consumption	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Total daily energy consumed by the household/system:
Net Grid Energy	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Daily net energy exchanged with the grid. Positive = net import; negative = net export.
Grid Import	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Total energy imported from the grid during the day (purchasing).
Grid Export	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Total energy exported to the grid during the day (feed-in).
Battery Charging	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Total energy stored in the battery during the day.
Battery Discharging	Aggregated (daily sum)	kWh	Total energy delivered by the battery during the day.
Mean Battery Power	Mean (daily average)	W	Average battery power over the day (positive = discharge, negative = charge).
Mean SoC	Mean (daily average)	%	battery State of Charge over the day.

Self-Consumption Ratio (SCR)	Derived	0–1	Share of PV used on-site
Grid Dependency Ratio (GDR)	Derived	0–1	Share of consumption supplied by grid
Battery Net Usage	Derived	kWh	Net battery contribution (discharging minus charging)
Day	Temporal	—	Day of month (1–31).
Month	Temporal	—	Calendar month (1–12).
Weekday	Temporal	—	Day of week (0 = Mon, 6= Sun).

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154 2.3 Outlier Detection

155 Before clustering, anomalous operational days were identified and removed using Isolation
 156 Forest [20], a tree-based anomaly detection algorithm effective for high-dimensional energy data.
 157 The algorithm constructs random decision trees and identifies outliers as points requiring fewer
 158 splits to isolate. A contamination parameter of 0.01 was used, corresponding to an expected 1%
 159 anomaly rate. Of 416 initial daily records, 5 days (1.2%) were flagged as outliers based on anomaly
 160 scores and excluded from subsequent analysis, yielding 411 normal operation days. This
 161 preprocessing step ensures that clustering captures genuine operational patterns rather than rare
 162 faults or measurement artifacts.

163 2.4 Feature Scaling and Dimensionality Reduction

164 Features were standardized using z-score normalization before clustering to balance
 165 magnitudes across variables with different units. The core feature set used for clustering includes:
 166 Daily PV Energy (kWh), Daily Consumption (kWh), Net Grid Energy (kWh), Grid Import (kWh),
 167 Grid Export (kWh), Battery Net Usage (kWh), Mean SoC (%), Self-Consumption Ratio, and Grid
 168 Dependency Ratio. Results were validated against min-max scaling and found to be robust; z-
 169 scores are reported for reproducibility.

170 To visualize the structure of the high-dimensional feature space, both linear and non-linear
 171 dimensionality reduction techniques were employed. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was
 172 used to project the data onto orthogonal axes of maximum variance and to interpret feature
 173 importance via the loading matrix [21]. t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) was
 174 computed to examine non-linear structures and cluster separation in low-dimensional space [22].
 175 t-SNE parameters were set to perplexity=30, learning rate=200, with 2,000 iterations and PCA
 176 initialization (random state=42). t-SNE was used for visualization only and not for clustering.

177 2.5 Clustering Algorithms and Method Comparison

178 Clustering was performed on the z-scored daily feature matrix to identify latent operational
 179 archetypes. Multiple algorithms were compared to ensure robustness and interpretability:

- 180 1. **K-means** with K-means++ initialization [9] for K=2-10 candidates, using 50 random
 181 initializations per K value.
- 182 2. **Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM)** with full covariance structure to capture ellipsoidal
 183 cluster shapes [23].

184 3. **Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering** with Ward linkage (Euclidean distance) to
185 examine dendrogram structure [24].

186 4. **DBSCAN** (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) [25] with epsilon
187 parameter tuned via k-nearest neighbors distance analysis.

188 Internal validation metrics including Silhouette coefficient, Davies-Bouldin index, and
189 Calinski-Harabasz score were computed for each method. Although DBSCAN achieved the
190 highest Silhouette score (0.285), it classified 6.8% of days as noise (cluster label -1), representing
191 data loss rather than improved clustering quality. K-means (Silhouette = 0.216) was selected for
192 final analysis because it assigns all days to interpretable operational modes without data exclusion,
193 identifies four distinct regimes consistent with system architecture, and provides stable centroids
194 for regime characterization. Cross-method agreement was quantified using Normalized Mutual
195 Information (NMI) and Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) between K-means and alternative methods.

196 The optimal number of clusters (K=4) was determined using the elbow criterion applied to
197 within-cluster sum of squares (inertia) and confirmed by silhouette analysis across K=2-10. The
198 solution with the lowest inertia across 50 random initializations was retained (fixed random seed
199 for reproducibility).

200 2.6 Weather Data and Multivariate Regression

201 Daily meteorological data for the study period were obtained from NASA POWER (Prediction
202 of Worldwide Energy Resources) [34], including solar irradiance (kWh/m²), ambient temperature
203 (°C), minimum and maximum temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), wind speed (m/s), and
204 precipitation (mm). These variables were merged with the clustered daily dataset by date.

205 To quantify weather effects on PV production within each operational regime, cluster-wise
206 multivariate ordinary least squares (OLS) regression was performed [26]. For clusters with
207 sufficient sample size ($n \geq 10$), daily PV energy was modeled as a linear function of key
208 meteorological variables according to:

$$209 E_{PV,i} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 I_i + \beta_2 T_i + \beta_3 H_i + \beta_4 W_i + \epsilon_i \quad (4)$$

210 where $E_{PV,i}$ is daily PV energy, I_i is irradiance, T_i is temperature, H_i is relative humidity, W_i is
211 wind speed, and ϵ_i is the error term. To enable direct comparison of effect sizes across variables
212 with different units, all predictors and the response were standardized (zero mean, unit variance)
213 within each cluster before regression, yielding standardized coefficients (β) that represent effect
214 sizes in standard deviation units [27]. Model fit was assessed using R^2 and adjusted R^2 to account
215 for differing sample sizes and predictor counts across clusters.

216 For Cluster 3, which contains only 5 days (1.2% of data), multivariate regression would be
217 unreliable due to insufficient degrees of freedom. Therefore, a univariate model using only
218 irradiance was fitted for this cluster, with other weather coefficients reported as not applicable.

219 Standardized coefficients allow direct interpretation: a one-standard-deviation increase in
220 irradiance corresponds to an increase of β^* standard deviations in daily PV energy, holding other
221 variables constant. This approach is consistent with recent PV studies that apply OLS to calculate

222 performance metrics [28] and enables identification of regime-specific sensitivities beyond simple
223 bivariate relationships.

224 3. Results

225 3.1 Clustering Robustness and Regime Selection

226 Table 2 summarizes the robustness analysis conducted across four clustering formulations, K-
227 means, Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and
228 DBSCAN, using internal validation metrics and coverage characteristics. The purpose of this
229 comparison is to assess the stability and interpretability of the identified operational regimes rather
230 than to identify a universally optimal clustering algorithm.

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232

Table 2. Clustering robustness and model adequacy analysis

Method	Silhouette	Davies–Bouldin	Calinski–Harabasz	Inertia	BIC	AIC	No. of Clusters	Noise Points
K-means	0.2161	1.3395	92.94	2233.01	–	–	4	0
GMM (full covariance)	–0.0045	2.9616	18.75	–	–3252.39	–4502.17	4	0
Hierarchical (Ward)	0.1976	1.4710	83.31	–	–	–	4	0
DBSCAN ($\epsilon = 1.87$)	0.2855	0.7637	18.61	–	–	–	3	28

233

234 Centroid based K-means, probabilistic GMM, and hierarchical clustering methods, which
235 enforce full assignment of observations, consistently converge to a four-cluster structure. This
236 consistency indicates the presence of a stable underlying regime decomposition in the daily PV
237 battery operational data. Among these methods, K-means and hierarchical clustering exhibit
238 comparable Silhouette and Calinski Harabasz values, suggesting moderate cluster separation with
239 clear inter-cluster structure. The K-means solution further provides stable centroids and complete
240 data coverage, which are essential for regime based operational analysis.

241 The GMM formulation evaluated with a full covariance structure yields lower Silhouette and
242 Calinski Harabasz scores. This outcome reflects the overlapping nature of probabilistic cluster
243 assignments rather than poor model adequacy. Importantly, GMM also identifies a four-
244 component structure, and the reported AIC and BIC values support this configuration. This
245 indicates that the regime separation is not an artifact of spherical clustering assumptions inherent
246 to K-means.

247 DBSCAN achieves higher compactness metrics, including the highest Silhouette and the
248 lowest Davies Bouldin index, due to its ability to isolate dense operational states. However, this

249 comes at the cost of excluding 28 operating days, corresponding to 6.8 % of the data, and yielding
 250 a three-cluster structure. Since the objective of this study is to characterize all daily operating
 251 conditions of the PV battery system, density-based clustering is unsuitable as the primary
 252 analytical model despite favorable compactness metrics.

253 Overall, Table 2 demonstrates that a four-regime structure is consistently supported across
 254 clustering formulations that preserve full temporal coverage, while density-based clustering
 255 emphasizes localized compactness at the expense of completeness. Based on interpretability,
 256 stability across initializations, and full assignment of operating days, K-means was retained as the
 257 primary model for subsequent regime characterization and weather sensitivity analysis.

258
 259 Figure 2. Projection of daily operating states onto the first two principal components for (a) K-means, (b) Gaussian
 260 Mixture Model with full covariance, (c) hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and (d) DBSCAN. The
 261 visualization illustrates consistency of the four-regime structure across full-assignment methods and the presence of
 262 noise points in density-based clustering.
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264 Figure 2 presents the projection of daily operating states onto the first two principal
 265 components for (a) K-means, (b) Gaussian Mixture Model with full covariance, (c) hierarchical

266 clustering with Ward linkage, and (d) DBSCAN. The visualization complements the quantitative
 267 results reported in Table 2. K-means and hierarchical clustering produce comparable regime
 268 separation with full data coverage, while GMM exhibits overlapping cluster densities reflecting
 269 probabilistic assignments. DBSCAN isolates dense operating states, but labels a subset of days as
 270 noise, which explains its exclusion from subsequent regime characterization.

271
 272 Figure 3. Agreement between clustering formulations measured by normalized mutual information

273 Figure 3 presents the pairwise Normalized Mutual Information (NMI) scores between
 274 clustering results obtained using K-means, Gaussian Mixture Models with full covariance,
 275 hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and DBSCAN, respectively. NMI quantifies the
 276 agreement between two clustering solutions, with values close to one indicating strong consistency
 277 and values near zero indicating weak correspondence. A high NMI value of 0.73 is observed
 278 between K-means and hierarchical clustering, indicating substantial agreement in cluster
 279 assignments between these two methods. This result confirms that the four-regime structure
 280 identified by K-means is not method-specific and is strongly supported by an independent
 281 hierarchical formulation, reinforcing the stability of the regime decomposition. In contrast, the
 282 agreement between K-means and GMM is relatively low, with an NMI of 0.11, while the

283 agreement between hierarchical clustering and GMM is 0.15. These lower values reflect the
284 probabilistic and overlapping nature of GMM cluster assignments, which differ conceptually from
285 the hard partitions produced by centroid-based and hierarchical methods. Despite this, GMM still
286 converges to a four-component structure, as reported in Table 2, supporting the adequacy of the
287 selected regime number while highlighting differences in cluster boundary representation. Finally,
288 DBSCAN exhibits consistently low NMI values with all other methods, ranging from 0.06 to 0.22,
289 indicating limited correspondence with full-assignment clustering approaches. This outcome is
290 expected, as DBSCAN identifies dense regions and labels a subset of observations as noise rather
291 than assigning all days to clusters. The weak agreement further supports the exclusion of DBSCAN
292 from subsequent regime characterization, despite its favorable compactness metrics reported in
293 Table 2.

294 Taken together, the NMI analysis complements the quantitative metrics in Table 2 and the
295 visual patterns shown in Figure 2 by demonstrating that the four-regime structure identified by K-
296 means is robust and consistently reproduced by hierarchical clustering, while alternative clustering
297 paradigms emphasize different aspects of the data structure. These results justify the selection of
298 K-means as the primary analytical model for regime interpretation and weather sensitivity analysis.

299 3.2 Intraday Operational Profiles of Identified Regimes

300 Figure 4 illustrates the characteristic intraday behavior associated with each operational
301 regime. Clear differences are observed in the magnitude and timing of PV production, household
302 demand, grid interaction, and battery charging and discharging patterns. Regime C0 exhibits lower
303 PV generation and moderate consumption, resulting in sustained grid import throughout the day.
304 Regime C1 is characterized by higher PV output and elevated daytime consumption, with reduced
305 grid dependency during peak solar hours. Regime C2 shows strong midday PV production
306 combined with active battery charging and subsequent discharge during evening demand peaks,
307 indicating effective load shifting. Regime C3 displays the highest variability, with pronounced
308 peaks in both PV production and battery power, reflecting days with high solar availability and
309 dynamic battery operation.

310
 311 **Figure 4.** Mean intraday profiles of: (a) PV production power, (b) household consumption power, (c) grid power
 312 exchange, and (d) battery power for the four operational regimes identified by K-means clustering. Shaded areas
 313 represent variability around the mean profiles across days within each regime.

314

315 3.3 Weather Sensitivity Across Operational Regimes

316 Table 3 summarizes the meteorological conditions associated with each operational regime.
 317 While all clusters are subject to broadly similar tropical climatic conditions, systematic differences
 318 in irradiance and atmospheric variables are observed across regimes.

319 Cluster C0 is characterized by the lowest mean irradiance and relatively high humidity,
 320 conditions that are consistent with its weaker PV energy response and lower effective utilization
 321 of solar resources. Cluster C1 experiences the highest irradiance levels and slightly reduced
 322 humidity, providing favorable conditions for PV generation despite high electricity demand in this
 323 regime. Cluster C2 exhibits elevated irradiance and higher maximum temperatures, aligning with
 324 its strong PV performance and enhanced self-consumption observed in the operational analysis.
 325 Cluster C3 corresponds to rare meteorological conditions with reduced irradiance and elevated

326 humidity. Due to the limited number of observations, results for this regime are interpreted
 327 cautiously.

328 Table 3 Meteorological conditions associated with operational regimes.

Cluster	N (days)	Irradiance (kWh/m ² /day)	Temperature (°C)	Min Temp (°C)	Max Temp (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Precipitation (mm/day)
C0	135	4.09 ± 1.54	27.45 ± 1.74	23.96 ± 2.47	31.82 ± 3.25	78.56 ± 15.55	2.35 ± 0.74	7.93 ± 10.06
C1	151	4.88 ± 1.21	27.72 ± 2.02	23.70 ± 2.51	32.46 ± 3.47	75.78 ± 15.89	1.94 ± 0.73	5.49 ± 10.64
C2	120	4.64 ± 1.50	28.25 ± 2.25	24.33 ± 2.42	33.05 ± 3.93	75.60 ± 17.54	2.17 ± 0.73	9.56 ± 20.24
C3	5	3.52 ± 1.82	27.56 ± 0.54	24.97 ± 0.70	30.68 ± 1.39	88.63 ± 4.11	2.21 ± 0.92	5.85 ± 3.85
Overall	411	4.54 ± 1.46	27.78 ± 2.02	23.99 ± 2.47	32.40 ± 3.55	76.80 ± 16.26	2.14 ± 0.75	7.49 ± 14.01

329
 330 Across all clusters, temperature ranges remain relatively narrow, indicating that irradiance and
 331 humidity are the primary drivers of regime differentiation rather than thermal extremes. These
 332 meteorological patterns provide physical context for the regime-dependent PV energy sensitivities
 333 quantified in the subsequent regression analysis.

334 Figure 5 illustrates the regime dependent relationship between daily solar irradiance and PV
 335 energy production. Distinct sensitivities to irradiance are observed across operational regimes, as
 336 reflected by differing slopes of the fitted lines. Regime C0 exhibits the weakest irradiance
 337 response, indicating lower effective PV utilization under similar solar conditions. Regime C1
 338 shows a stronger and more consistent irradiance–production relationship, reflecting improved
 339 alignment between PV generation and system operation. Regime C2 demonstrates high PV output
 340 across a wide irradiance range, suggesting favorable operating conditions and effective system
 341 utilization. Regime C3 exhibits the steepest apparent slope; however, this result should be
 342 interpreted with caution due to the limited sample size of this regime.

Figure 5. Irradiance–PV energy relationship across operational regimes

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Figure 6 quantifies the relative influence of meteorological variables on daily PV energy production across operational regimes using standardized regression coefficients. Irradiance is the dominant driver in all regimes, with substantially higher effect sizes in Regimes C1 and C2 compared to C0, indicating more efficient conversion of solar resource into energy output under these operating conditions. Temperature exhibits a weak negative association in Regime C0 and modest positive effects in Regimes C1 and C2, suggesting regime dependent thermal sensitivity. Relative humidity shows a notable positive contribution in Regime C2, reflecting atmospheric conditions associated with high PV output days. Wind speed effects are comparatively small across regimes, indicating a secondary role in daily PV energy variability. For Regime C3, the estimated irradiance coefficient is large; however, this result should be interpreted with caution due to the limited number of observations.

358
 359 Figure 6. Multivariate weather effects on PV energy across operational regimes (Standardized regression coefficients
 360 (β^*) from cluster wise regression models linking daily PV energy to meteorological variables. Bars represent effect
 361 sizes for irradiance, temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed within each operational regime. For Cluster 3,
 362 only a univariate model with irradiance was estimated due to limited sample size.)
 363

364 Table 4 reports the standardized regression coefficients (β^*) and goodness-of-fit statistics from
 365 cluster-wise regression models linking daily PV energy to meteorological variables. For Clusters
 366 0–2, multivariate models including irradiance, temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed
 367 were estimated. For Cluster 3, only a univariate model with irradiance was fitted due to the limited
 368 sample size ($N = 5$). Across all operational regimes, irradiance is the dominant explanatory
 369 variable, with standardized coefficients increasing from Cluster 0 ($\beta^* = 0.22$) to Cluster 3 ($\beta^* =$
 370 0.79). This monotonic increase indicates progressively stronger coupling between solar resource
 371 availability and PV energy output across the identified regimes. Cluster 0 exhibits weak weather
 372 sensitivity, reflected by a low R^2 value (0.03) and near-zero adjusted R^2 . This regime corresponds
 373 to operating conditions where PV production is weakly constrained by irradiance, likely due to
 374 system-level limitations such as storage saturation or load-dominated operation. Clusters 1 and 2
 375 display substantially higher explanatory power, with adjusted R^2 values of 0.29 and 0.19,
 376 respectively. In these regimes, irradiance remains the primary driver of PV energy, while
 377 temperature and relative humidity contribute secondary but non-negligible effects. Notably,
 378 relative humidity shows a pronounced positive effect in Cluster 2 ($\beta^* = 0.37$), suggesting regime-
 379 specific atmospheric influences on PV performance beyond irradiance alone. Cluster 3 exhibits
 380 the strongest irradiance dependence, with a univariate R^2 of 0.62. Although this regime contains
 381 only five days and is therefore not suitable for multivariate inference, the high explanatory power
 382 indicates extreme operating conditions dominated by solar availability. Results for this cluster are
 383 reported for completeness, but are interpreted cautiously.

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Table 4. Cluster-wise regression results linking daily PV energy to meteorological variables.

Cluster	Feature	β^* (unitless)	R ²	Adjusted R ²	N	Model
0	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.2196	0.0296	-0.0002	135	Multivariate
0	Temperature (°C)	-0.0855	0.0296	-0.0002	135	Multivariate
0	RH (%)	0.1076	0.0296	-0.0002	135	Multivariate
0	Wind (m/s)	-0.0253	0.0296	-0.0002	135	Multivariate
1	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.5684	0.3122	0.2934	151	Multivariate
1	Temperature (°C)	0.0728	0.3122	0.2934	151	Multivariate
1	RH (%)	0.0886	0.3122	0.2934	151	Multivariate
1	Wind (m/s)	-0.0295	0.3122	0.2934	151	Multivariate
2	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.6354	0.2215	0.1944	120	Multivariate
2	Temperature (°C)	0.1378	0.2215	0.1944	120	Multivariate
2	RH (%)	0.3695	0.2215	0.1944	120	Multivariate
2	Wind (m/s)	0.0835	0.2215	0.1944	120	Multivariate
3	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.7905	0.6249	0.4999	5	Univariate
3	Temperature (°C)	-	0.6249	0.4999	5	Univariate
3	RH (%)	-	0.6249	0.4999	5	Univariate
3	Wind (m/s)	-	0.6249	0.4999	5	Univariate

386 In summary, the regression results demonstrate that the identified operational regimes are not
 387 only statistically distinct but also physically meaningful, exhibiting clear differences in weather
 388 sensitivity and explanatory structure. This regime-dependent behavior supports the effectiveness
 389 of the clustering framework in capturing heterogeneous PV–battery system dynamics.

3.4 Operational Implications of Identified Regimes

390
391

Table 5. Key operational characteristics of PV–battery regimes

Cluster	N (days)	PV Energy (kWh/day)	Consumption (kWh/day)	Grid Import (kWh/day)	Battery Discharge (kWh/day)	Mean SoC (%)	SCR (%)	SSR (%)
C0	135	33.42 ± 11.56	69.87 ± 18.44	42.57 ± 12.54	9.28 ± 7.07	98.6 ± 2.1	78.8 ± 19.9	38.3 ± 13.3
C1	151	47.80 ± 12.62	105.82 ± 18.15	70.11 ± 10.81	22.71 ± 13.44	95.8 ± 5.7	72.6 ± 24.5	32.6 ± 12.2
C2	120	55.30 ± 11.28	92.99 ± 16.79	41.68 ± 9.65	29.73 ± 10.47	87.5 ± 12.7	92.9 ± 15.9	54.9 ± 9.2
C3	5	44.01 ± 19.19	86.50 ± 18.43	50.80 ± 14.70	25.07 ± 19.32	85.3 ± 15.9	79.8 ± 7.9	41.0 ± 16.8

392 Table 5 summarizes the key operational characteristics of the four identified PV–battery
 393 regimes. Clear differences in energy balance, grid reliance, and storage utilization are observed
 394 across clusters, confirming the physical relevance of the regime decomposition. Cluster C0
 395

396 represents low-generation operating conditions, with the lowest PV energy output and moderate
 397 electricity demand. This regime relies substantially on grid imports and exhibits limited battery
 398 discharge, resulting in relatively low self-sufficiency despite moderate self-consumption levels.
 399 Cluster C1 is the most frequent regime and corresponds to high-demand operating conditions.
 400 Although PV generation is higher than in C0, electricity consumption remains dominant, leading
 401 to the highest grid import levels among all clusters. Also, battery discharge is more pronounced,
 402 but self-sufficiency remains limited, indicating load-driven operation.

403 Cluster C2 reflects the most favorable operating regime, characterized by the highest PV
 404 energy production and substantial battery discharge. This regime achieves the highest self-
 405 consumption and self-sufficiency ratios, indicating effective coordination between PV generation,
 406 storage utilization, and local demand. The lower mean state of charge further suggests active
 407 battery cycling to support local energy autonomy. Cluster C3 captures rare operating conditions
 408 and accounts for a small fraction of the dataset. While PV production and battery discharge are
 409 comparable to intermediate regimes, the limited sample size warrants cautious interpretation. This
 410 regime is retained for completeness but does not influence the dominant operational patterns.

411 Taken together, these results demonstrate that the identified clusters correspond to distinct and
 412 interpretable operating modes of the PV–battery system, ranging from grid-dependent to highly
 413 self-sufficient conditions. This regime-specific characterization provides a meaningful basis for
 414 subsequent weather sensitivity analysis.

415
 416 Figure 7. Temporal distribution of operational regimes from August 2024 to July 2025.

417 Figure 7 illustrates the temporal evolution of operational regimes over the study period. Clear
 418 seasonal patterns are observed in regime prevalence, indicating that PV–battery system behavior
 419 varies systematically over time. Regime C2 dominates during late monsoon and early dry-season
 420 months, reflecting periods of favorable PV generation and high self-consumption. Regime C1
 421 becomes prevalent during the transition months toward the dry season, consistent with increased
 422 electricity demand and active battery utilization. Regime C0 occurs most frequently during mid-

423 year months, indicating operating conditions characterized by lower PV contribution and increased
424 grid reliance. Regime C3 appears only sporadically and contributes negligibly to monthly
425 distributions, confirming its role as a rare operating mode. The observed temporal structure
426 reinforces the physical interpretability of the identified regimes and suggests that seasonal and
427 climatic factors play a key role in shaping long-term PV–battery system operation.

428 4. Engineering Implications

429 The identified operational regimes provide a practical abstraction for interpreting and
430 managing residential photovoltaic battery systems beyond day-to-day variability. First, regime
431 labels can serve as high-level inputs to energy management systems or model predictive control
432 frameworks, enabling controllers to adapt strategies based on expected operating conditions rather
433 than raw time-series data alone. Second, regime-aware photovoltaic forecasting can improve
434 prediction robustness by conditioning forecasts on operational context, particularly during
435 transitions between grid-dependent and self-sufficient modes. Third, the quantified regime-
436 specific energy balances and weather sensitivities offer decision support for tariff design and
437 battery sizing by revealing how storage utilization and grid reliance vary across operating modes.
438 In addition, long-term monitoring of regime frequency and transitions can support degradation
439 detection and performance diagnosis, as shifts in regime distributions may indicate battery aging,
440 control drift, or changes in household behavior. Because the framework relies on commonly
441 available operational measurements, these implications are directly applicable to real-world
442 residential deployments without additional sensing requirements. Overall, the regime-based
443 perspective complements existing control and planning approaches by providing an interpretable
444 layer that links data-driven analysis with engineering decision-making.

445 5. Conclusion

446 This study presented a comprehensive, label-free analytical framework to uncover and
447 interpret long-term operational regimes of a residential photovoltaic–battery system using high-
448 resolution time-series data. By integrating daily feature engineering, robust outlier detection,
449 unsupervised clustering, and regime-specific weather regression, the proposed approach provides
450 a holistic understanding of how PV production, household demand, battery operation, and grid
451 interaction jointly shape daily system behavior.

452 Four distinct operational regimes were consistently identified and validated across multiple
453 clustering formulations. These regimes represent physically meaningful operating modes ranging
454 from grid-dependent, low-generation conditions to highly self-sufficient operation with active
455 battery cycling. Intraday profiles and aggregated performance metrics confirmed clear differences
456 in energy balance, storage utilization, and grid reliance across regimes. In particular, the most
457 favorable regime achieved the highest self-consumption and self-sufficiency ratios through

458 effective coordination between PV generation and battery discharge, while demand-dominated
459 regimes remained strongly dependent on grid imports despite substantial solar availability.

460 The cluster-wise regression analysis revealed pronounced regime-dependent weather
461 sensitivities. Solar irradiance was the dominant driver of PV energy production in all regimes, but
462 its explanatory power increased systematically from low-performance to high-performance
463 operating modes. Temperature and relative humidity exerted secondary but non-negligible
464 influences that varied across regimes, highlighting the importance of contextualizing weather
465 effects within operational states rather than treating all days as homogeneous. Temporal analysis
466 further demonstrated that regime occurrence is seasonally structured, reflecting the combined
467 influence of climatic conditions and household behavior over time.

468 Collectively, these findings demonstrate that unsupervised learning can effectively capture
469 heterogeneous and evolving PV–battery system dynamics without reliance on labeled data or
470 predefined operating rules. The proposed framework provides a practical basis for regime-aware
471 forecasting, adaptive control strategies, and tariff or incentive design that reflect real operating
472 behavior rather than average conditions. While the analysis focused on a single residential system
473 in a tropical climate, the methodology is readily transferable to other prosumer systems, climates,
474 and scales.

475 Future work may extend this framework by incorporating multiple households to assess regime
476 generalizability, integrating probabilistic or nonlinear regression models for weather sensitivity,
477 and embedding regime labels into real-time energy management systems. Such extensions would
478 further enhance the role of data-driven, interpretable analytics in supporting resilient and efficient
479 integration of distributed energy resources.

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495 review & editing. Eftichios Koutroulis: Validation, review & editing, Supervision. Dagmar
496 Juchelkova: Funding acquisition, review & editing, Supervision.

497 Availability of data and materials

498 Anonymized data and instruments (in digital format) from this research can be made available at
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